

Effect of Hatha Yoga and Aerobic Dance Practice on Interest of Adolescent Boys

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Abstract

Yoga is an ancient Indian Philosophy. The purpose of the study was to evaluate psychological response, to find out the changes in interest, following the Yoga and aerobic dance practices. The total subjects were 120 divided into four boys groups and their age ranges from 12–16 years. The duration of total practice period were 6 weeks (3 days in a week for 30 minutes). Pre test and post test data were analyzed by paired 't' test method. For obtaining the significant differences ANCOVA method was adopted

Key words : Yoga, Aerobic dance, Interest.

Introduction :

Yoga is science of life which helps man to attain his highest potential and highest state or consciousness. It has various psychological techniques involving asanas, Pranayamas etc. The term Yoga is applied to the attainment of highest aim, i.e. integration of personality as well as the various methods and techniques used for the fulfilment of that aim.

The origin of hatha yoga developed in India. In Sanskrit, 'Ha' means 'Sun' and 'Tha' means Moon. 'Hatha' means 'forceful' implying that powerful work must be done to purify the body. Yoga means to yoke, or to join two things together, hence hatha yoga is meant to join together sun (masculine, active) energy with the moon (feminine, receptive) energy, thus producing balance and greater power in an individual. It is the branch of Yoga which concentrates on physical health and mental well being. Hatha

Yoga uses bodily postures (asanas) with the goal of bringing about a sound healthy body and clear, peaceful mind.

It work to make the spine supple and to promote circulation of all organs, glands and tissues. Hatha yoga postures also stretch and align the body promoting balance and flexibility. Aerobic exercises such as aerobic dance, is a fun way to get fit. It combines fat-burning aerobic movements. music. In this article an attempt has been made to observe the improvement occur in the psychological variables following aerobic and Yoga practices among the adolescent. Aerobic dance and Hatha yoga have to produce improvements in psychological well being. All ages can benefit from aerobic dance. Aerobic dance is a popular exercise in adolescent pupil.

Purpose of the Study :

The purpose of the study was as follows :

- i) To observe the impact of hatha yoga and aerobic dance practice of adolescent boys.
- ii) To find out the changes if any in interest, following the yoga and aerobic practices.

Methodology :

The total subjects were one hundred and twenty (120) selected from the school of Rabindra Vidyapith high school, Santipur Nadia ,West Bengal. and age ranging from 12–16 years. All the subjects were possessed sound physique. All the subjects were divided into four groups i.e. Hatha Yoga, aerobic dance, combined and control groups.

a) Practice Schedule :

The total period of treatments were 6 weeks and each group practiced three days in a week and duration were 30 minutes which supervised exercise program for experimental subjects and control group continued usual activity. The subjects practiced the Asanas and Pranayamas.

Yoga Group : Practiced Tadasana, Tratoch ,Tadasana, Chakrasana, Surya Namaskar, Sarbangasana Halasana, Paschimothanasana and Pranayams were Nadi Sodhana, Kapalbhathi, Bhamari, Yoga-Nidra.

Aerobic Dance Group : Practiced aerobic dance with music.

Combined Group : Practiced Yoga 15 min. / day and aerobic 15 min. / day approximately.

Control group : The control group subjects were continued usual activity.

b) Criteria measured :

Age, height and weight were measured by school record, stadiometer and weighing machine accordingly. interest was measured by Questionnaire Method. Experimental subjects completed a 6-week supervised exercise program. Control subjects continued usual activity. The subjects were practice the Asanas & pranayama 30 minutes / day & thrice a week Asanas were Tadasana,Tratoch, Tadasana, chakrasana, Surja namaskar, Sarbagasana, Halasana etc. and Pranayamas were Bhastrika, Kapal bhathi, Bhamari etc. Aerobic dance with music also were practiced thrice a week and 30 mins. / day. For statistical analysis standard procedures have been adapted. Mean and SD were first computed. Then pretest and post test data were analyzed by paired 't' test method (Garrett, 1981). For obtaining the significant differences ANCOVA method (Garrett, 1981) was adopted.

Result and Discussion :

For testing the differences between mean scores selected psychological variables of Hatha Yoga Group, Aerobic Dance Group, Combined Group (Hatha Yoga and Aerobic Dance) as Control Group of subjects. The level of significance were at 0.05 and 0.01 of confidence. The mean and SD of their personal data (age, height and weight) were recorded on Table 1(a) & 1(b).

Table – 1(a)

Pretest : (Mean ± SD) of Yoga, aerobic dance, combined and control group variables

	Yoga Gr. Mean ± SD	Aerobic Dance Gr. Mean ± SD	Combined Gr. Mean ± SD	Control Gr. Mean ± SD
Personal Data				
Age	13.77 ± 1.25	13.8 ± 0.81	14.67 ± 0.99	14.90 ± 0.92
Height	141.70 ± 6.10	149.37 ± 4.43	151.3 ± 9.08	150.30 ± 8.54
Weight	38.67 ± 5.96	42.23 ± 4.72	42.70 ± 7.00	40.77 ± 5.16
Psychological Variable				
Interest	120.47±12.88	122.80 ± 9.28	122.03 ± 15.79	125.63± 11.18

Table – 1(b)

Posttest : (Mean ± SD) of Yoga, aerobic dance, combined and control group variables

	Yoga Gr. Mean ± SD	Aerobic Dance Gr. Mean ± SD	Combined Gr. Mean ± SD	Control Gr. Mean ± SD
Personal Data				
Weight	37.13 ± 5.48	40.20 ± 4.24	41.70 ± 6.22	41.33 ± 5.40
Psychological Variable				
Interest	127.63 ± 9.36	131.10 ± 6.22	130.63 ± 10.93	119.63 ± 9.56

Personal Data :

The age, height and weight of the subjects had been considered as personal variable.

Age : Mean scores and standard deviation of four groups of age were 13.77 ± 1.25 , 13.8 ± 0.81 , 14.67 ± 0.99 and 14.90 ± 0.92 years respectively in Table – 1(a).

Height : Mean scores and standard deviation of four groups of height were 141.70 ± 6.10 , 149.37 ± 4.43 , 151.37 ± 9.08 and 150.30 ± 8.54 cm. respectively in Table–1(a).

Weight : Mean scores and standard deviation of four groups of weight in pre-test were 38.67 ± 5.96 , 42.23 ± 4.72 , 42.70 ± 7.00 and 40.77 ± 5.16 kg respectively in Table–1(a) and Fig. No. 1. Post test weights mean and SD were 37.13 ± 5.48 , 40.20 ± 4.24 , 41.70 ± 6.22 and 41.33 ± 5.40 kg respectively in Table No.–1(b) and Fig. 1. After completion of the training programme mean scores of weight of all experimental groups were decreased slightly.

Psychological Variable(Interest) :

In my study I taken a psychological factors , Interest which is essential for any type of exercises programme.

Table – 1

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for interest among the four groups

	Sources of Variation	Ss	df	Ms	F
Pre Test	Between groups	421.27	3	140.42	0.90
	Within groups	18158.20	116	156.54	

	Total	18579.47	119		
Post Test	Between groups	2532.90	3	140.42	10.02
	Within groups	9775.60	116	156.54	
	Total	12308.50	119		

$F_{0.05} = 2.68$, $F_{0.01} = 3.96$

F is significant at both levels in post test.

Table – 2

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for interest among the groups

Source of Variation	df	SS _{X.Y}	SS _{Y.X}	MS _{Y.X} (V _{Y.X})	F _{Y.X}	SD _{Y.X}
Among Gr. Means	3	-752.07	3444.43	1148.14	31.51	6.04
Within Gr. SS	115	10071.07	4189.89	36.43		
Total	118	9319.00	7634.32			

$F_{0.05} = 2.68$, $F_{0.01} = 3.96$, F is significant at both levels.

Table – 3

Significance of difference among adjusted Y Means of interest

Variables	SE _d	df	Diff. Adjusted Mean	Sig. at 0.05 or 0.01
Yoga vs. Aerobic Dance Gr.	1.56	115	2.17	NS

Yoga vs. Combined Gr.	1.56	115	2.13	NS
Yoga vs. Control Gr.	1.56	115	10.87**	0.01
Aerobic dance vs. Combined Gr.	1.56	115	0.04	NS
Aerobic dance vs. Control Gr.	1.56	115	13.04**	0.01
Combined vs. Control Gr.	1.56	115	13.00**	0.01

*Sig. at 0.05 level, **Sig. at 0.01 level, NS is Non-significant.

Table – 4

Represents the adjusted Y means of Interest

Groups	Mean X	Mean Y	Mean Y.X (adj.)
Yoga	120.47	127.63	128.89
Aerobic dance	122.80	131.10	131.06
Combined Y & A	122.03	130.63	131.02
Control	125.63	119.63	118.02

Pre test – X, Post test – Y.

Fig. 1. Pretest & Posttest Means of Interest of Four Groups

From the Table No. 1(a) & 1(b) it was found that mean scores and SD of interest before training of all the groups were 120.47 ± 12.88 , 122.80 ± 9.28 , 122.03 ± 15.79 , 125.63 ± 11.18 and after training were 127.63 ± 9.36 , 131.10 ± 6.22 , 130.63 ± 10.93 , 119.63 ± 9.56 respectively.

Participating in Yoga and aerobic dance programme in interest all the mean scores of experimental groups were increased. Since all the mean scores of interest were not equal, analysis of variance was computed in the Table No. 1 to find the significant differences among the four means. It was observed from the Table No.2 ANCOVA was done to find out the significant effect after participating the exercise programme among the groups. All the experimental groups were increased their interest at 0.01 level as compared to control group. So treatment had positive effect on the groups. In post test interest of aerobic dance group was better than other three groups.

Conclusions :

On the basis of the results and discussions, I conclude the specific conclusions which are given bellow.

- (i) All the experimental boys groups increased their interest following the aerobic dance and yoga practice and it was significant at 0.01 level in compare to the control boys group.
- (ii) The organized Yoga and aerobic dance program in the boys subjects participated for about six week is definitely improved their performance in interest.

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